

**MEMBERS OF SOCIETY IN THE UPBRINGING OF YOUNG
PEOPLE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE**

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Annotation. In this article, we have learned the theoretical knowledge of the relationships between family and neighborhoods, as well as some recommendations for further development of our relationships. In the upbringing of young people in the mahallas we need to use the method of our ancestors, to be based on our historical tradition and our national education. The most important element in the field of education is the universal human and national cultural values. This is the training of young people on the basis of the historical, national cultural heritage, the traditions of national education that have been formed over thousands of years.

Key words: high intelligence, social activity, spiritual and moral education, diligence, national pride, patriotism, national traditions, internationalism.

Strengthening the independence of our state, the fate of its reforms in socio-economic, legal education and other spheres, the establishment of a great future of our country directly depends on the level of spiritual and moral upbringing of citizens, especially the younger generation, their high consciousness, social activity. Therefore, our country has been paying special attention to issues of spiritual and moral education since the first days of independence as one of the priorities of state policy.

As we all know, educational work in the life of society has always been and remains relevant. The fact that Abdullah Avlani, a 20th-century educator, argued that education is a matter of life or life, or salvation, or destruction, or calamity, for us. The transformation of educational work in our country into a priority at the state level is also proof of how important work it is in our society to educate young people as personnel with spiritual perfection, strength, knowledge and high thinking. It is becoming clear that the role of family and neighborhood in the spiritual education of the younger generation is incomparable, the need to further strengthen and improve mutual cooperation between them.

At this point, our President Sh. The following thoughts of Mirziyoyev emphasize that youth education is one of the urgent tasks of today: □another

important issue that always makes us think about is the etiquette, behavior, in a word, the worldview of our youth. Today The Times are changing rapidly. Who makes these changes feel more than everyone else - young people. May young people be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, do not forget about oneself. Let the call to who we are, what kind of generation we are, always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to remain true to their self. What do we achieve at the expense of this? We will achieve at the expense of upbringing, upbringing and only upbringing.

Family and neighborhood are equally responsible for raising our young people to become spiritually mature. To do this, first of all, the parents, the neighborhood should be an example, an example to young people on all fronts. In the spiritual education of young people, family and neighborhood work together, these educational institutions can achieve great efficiency in the work of upbringing.

The tasks of the family in raising the younger generation are mainly to create a healthy atmosphere in the family, to take into account the national spirit and lifestyle, to make parents instructive for children, to form a feeling of love for parents, motherland, to ensure mutual care, to improve legal education in the family, to ensure that family members realize their rights and duties, it consists in creating an economic and social environment for children to be spiritually harmonious and physically healthy, teaching children to think independently, raising them in the spirit of independence ideas and devotion to national thinking.

Including the meaningful Organization of children's free time from a pedagogical point of view, providing them with additional education, creating the necessary conditions for the development of talent buds present in their children, being responsible in the family so that their child can fully fulfill their duties to the educational institution, neighborhood, State and society, parents constantly increase their pedagogical and psychological level of knowledge,

At the same time, a number of tasks are set before the neighborhood in the upbringing and upbringing of a harmonious personality. Including:

- participation by neighborhood activists in the discussion of issues that should be carried out in the educational process in conjunction with educational institutions and activism in finding rational solutions;
- discuss spiritually unhealthy families at neighborhood gatherings, take community action against them, and support the provision of economic and social assistance to educational institutions in the neighborhood area;
- and through parents to encourage students in every possible way to instill their qualities such as Initiative, hard work, national pride, patriotism, national decency, internationalism;

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

-to influence young people through religious sects and sects, through parents to correctly understand the essence of fanaticism, and mobilize the public to instill in them the educational oaths of our great ancestors;

-active involvement of various foundations, women's committees, various societies associations and creative associations in the work of educating young people on the basis of ideas of national independence, finding solutions to problems;

- Organization of various competitions, sports competitions, conferences, celebrations and competitions together with educational institutions in the territory of the neighborhood;

-social and material support of talented young people in different directions, popularization of the experience of the life of exemplary families with positive results in education and upbringing;

- Organization of classes "family lessons" in the territory of the Neighborhood, Organization of activities of various circles and clubs using the capabilities of folk Masters, artists, intellectuals and all creative people living in the neighborhood;

-love for Uzbekistan, its nature in youth, interest in its history, preservation of national traditions, contribution to the development of our Country, neighborhood improvement, formation of a sense of responsibility for the population;

- implementation of various activities in cooperation with an educational institution to provide legal, spiritual, educational, social concepts;

-it is envisaged to ensure that all educational, spiritual, educational, cultural-mass and sports activities carried out in residential areas, neighborhoods will be carried out, such as achieving the center of the neighborhood.

As shown above, the neighborhood serves as a huge spiritual upbringing, relying on long-standing deeds, Customs and traditions. Through the pand-exhortation of the elderly, the personal lesson of adults, the solidarity of the community, ideas of goodness are instilled in the minds of people.

Indeed, the role of the mahalas in the proper education of young people in the family is very large. Because the neighborhood has served as a community that unites people, has social-political, cultural-educational and educational value.

It is necessary to carry out the following work with the families of the neighborhood in order to maintain the spiritual and educational environment in the neighborhoods and increase their efficiency, based on the tasks set before the families and neighborhoods mentioned above:

- to establish a working group and determine its composition in order to achieve the effectiveness of educational work carried out in the neighborhood;

- improve the spiritual service of students, youth in the neighborhood, create favorable conditions for them, organize clubs, clubs, build sports facilities and attract a wide range;

-celebrating the birth date of Imam al-Bukhari, Bakhoviddin Naqshbandi, Zamaghshariy, Termiziy, Farghani, al Khwarazmi and others) with the people of the neighborhood;

-wide celebration of Independence Day, Constitution Day, teachers and coaches Day, Women's day, defender of the Fatherland Day, Navruz holiday, Ramadan and Kurban Hayit;

- instilling patriotic feelings in students, young people in the neighborhood;

- to reveal the essence of the reforms in all areas of our country today;

- strengthening feelings of national pride, self-sacrifice in the youth of the neighborhood;

- promotion of ideas of independence, ideology of national independence among the inhabitants of the neighborhood;

- it was shown to young people in the neighborhood who want to create the necessary opportunities, etc.

Knowledge of beautiful and symbolic traditions inherited from our ancestors, participation in them directly and knowledge of the procedure for conducting these traditions, the rules of Law, plays an important educational role in the spiritual formation of young people.

This is how the task of composing such skills and abilities from young people is assigned, first of all, to the family, to the neighborhood community.

The establishment of youth education begins first of all with the family. Especially in the context of the Uzbek family, such human qualities as kindness, respect for parents, faithfulness to the duties before them, love for the mother-motherland are formed in the family.

However, our honorable first president I.A.Karimov had stated that it would be the same mudao to build the spiritual climate of any household on the basis of mutual-respect, morality, human relations in order to avoid mistakes in the matter of Family Education." It should be remembered that in the family, a parent should be a school of remembrance for his children, with devotion to their profession, kindness to the living land, behavior, mutual respect for each other, how much they fulfill their duties to society and the state.

The position of the family in society is so high that it does not fit into the definition of Hecht. In the family, the fruit of parental labor grows. Children are the continuation of the life of the parent, from whom he inherits good and good, which,

in turn, he conveys to the offspring. That is why there is no more hard work in this world than raising children.

A person who is not happy in his family cannot be happy anywhere. That is why, above all, we need to pay a lot of attention to spiritual education in our families. Only then will the family be strong.

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